

Social Work Practice to Labour Welfare: A Proposed Model of Field Work Practicum and Role of Social Worker in India

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Abstract—Social work is a professional activity based on the approach of “helping people to help themselves” (Stroup). Social work education and practice both are based on humanitarian philosophy in which social workers try to increase the happiness of the society and to reduce the problems of society. Labour welfare is a specialised field of social work which especially focuses on welfare of organised and unorganised labour. In India labour is facing numerous problems in both organised and unorganised sectors because of ignorance, illiteracy, high rate of unemployment etc. In most of the Indian social work institutions we have this specialization with different names like Human Resource Management or Industrial Relation and Personnel Management or Industrial Relations and Labour Welfare or Industrial Social Work etc. Field work practice is integrated part of social work education curriculum in all specialised field. In India we have different field work practice models being followed in different institutions. The main objective of this paper is to prepare a universal field work practicum model in the field of labour welfare. This paper is exploratory in nature, researcher used personal experience and secondary data (model of field work practice in different institutions like Aligarh Muslim University, Pondicherry University, Central University of Karnataka, University of Lucknow, MJP Rohilkhand University Bareilly etc.) Researcher found that there is an immediate need to upgrade the curriculum or field work practice in this particular field, as more than 40 percent of total population engaged in either unorganised or organised sector (NSSO 2011-12) and they are not aware about their rights. In this way a social worker can play an important role in existing labour welfare facilities by making them aware.

Keywords—Fieldwork, labour welfare, organised labour, social work practice, unorganised labour.

I. MEANING OF SOCIAL WORK

MEANING of social work is not so easy to understand in Indian context. In India we have three meaning of social work in different connotation. Sometime it looks very easy to understand and another time so complex and dynamic, it means it is more or less impossible to give a universally accepted meaning or definition of social work in Indian perspective.

II. MEANING OF SOCIAL WORK TO A LAYMAN, SEMI-PROFESSIONAL AND PROFESSIONAL

- Layman’s view of social work is limited to the understanding of simply helping or serving others. This is

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an interpretation or self understood meaning of a common man about social work which is far away from the meaning of professional social work.

- Semi-professional perspective of social work is driven by people who are trained to work in professional welfare agency. They think they are working in welfare agency that’s why they have right to be called as a social worker.
- Professional meaning of social work includes person who has acquired degree in social work i.e. Master of Social Work (MSW)/Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)/M.A. (Social Work) or any other higher degree in Social Work and believe in the basic tenets of social work profession like, scientific knowledge, professional organizations, ethical values social approval etc. consider as a professional social worker [1].

III. SCIENTIFIC MEANING OR UNIVERSAL DEFINITION OF SOCIAL WORK

This universal and world wide acceptable definition is given by International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW) and International Association of School Social Work (IASSW), which focuses on practice based nature of social work, also it discusses various dimensions which play a vital role in the success of social work profession i.e. social justice, social change, social development, empowerment of people, human rights, etc. are the key components to Social work profession, which directly or indirectly focusses on the wellbeing of human being [2]. This comprehensive definition of social work includes all important aspects of human growth and development.

IV. LABOUR WELFARE

Labour welfare is a comprehensive term which includes overall welfare of labour. Different scholars explained labour welfare on different ways, according to most of the scholars’ point of view labour welfare includes health facilities, safety facilities, sitting facilities, canteen facilities, first aid facilities, washing and drying facilities, crèches room facility, housing facility, recreational facility, etc. It believes that such welfare facilities increase productivity, morale, motivational level, standard of living of workers.

V. FIELD WORK IN SOCIAL WORK

Field work is integral part of social work education [3], without Field Work knowledge social work education is not

complete. Field work considers learning by doing [3]. Field Work Practicum is also a dynamic, energetic and self-motivated course of action that helps students to pertain social work knowledge, skills, values, tools, principles and techniques of social work within an organization and community [3]. Field work practice is an important curriculum part of post graduate and undergraduate level social work student to apply social work theoretical knowledge into field [3]. Field work Practicum is an empirical evaluation and assessment of students' development. In this profession students of social work are given enough opportunities to use their academic knowledge and practical experiences in the society at all levels. Almost all field work activities are done under the guidance of supervisor. Social work students take part in several activities of the society to enhance the functioning of the society at all levels, and become familiar with the many components of the social work profession and its varied roles [4].

VI. INTERRELATION BETWEEN SOCIAL WORK, LABOUR WELFARE AND FIELD WORK PRACTICE

Labour welfare is a field of social work and an important function of human resource management. Human resource management is a highly specialised field of social work. Moreover, social work education concentrate on social welfare and labour welfare is a part of social welfare. In social work education we have field work as an integrated part of social work education. To understand the functioning of human resource manager and labour welfare officer social work students go to the industries to gain practical knowledge for same purpose. In industry a social worker learn different functions of HRM, labour welfare is one of the function of HRM. To understand the concept of labour welfare we have modules of International Labour Organization (ILO) and more than 40 labour legislations enacted in India to protect the interest of workers [5]. Some of important legislations are:

1. The Industrial Disputes Act, 1947
2. The Industrial Employment (Standing Order) Act, 1946
3. The Factories Act, 1948
4. The Workmen Compensation Act, 1923
5. The Minimum Wages Act, 1948
6. The Payment of Wages Act, 1936
7. The Motor Transport Workers Act, 1961
8. The Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
9. The Payment of Bonus Act, 1965
10. The Trade Union Act, 1926
11. The Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972
12. The Child Labour (Prohibition & Regulation) Act, 1986
13. The Contract Labour (R & A) Act, 1970
14. The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961
15. The Apprentices Act, 1961
16. The Employees' State Insurance Act, 1948
17. The Employees' Provident Fund and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 [5], [6]

On the basis of these labour legislations and the conceptual framework of labour welfare of ILO here research scholar is designing a model of field work practicum in the field of

labour welfare. These labour legislations are basic guidelines to improve overall social, economic, political, personal and professional condition of labour in India as well as it also will help the student to learn practical implications of labour legislations in India.

VII. PROBLEMS FACED BY SOCIAL WORK TRAINEES DURING MSW/BSW IN INDIA WHILE DOING FIELD WORK

In India there are more than 400 social work institutions which are offering BSW/MSW/MA (Social Work). When we talk about theoretical perspective of social work education it is good but practical part of social work education is not as it should be. In India we are lagging behind in the field of practical part of social work education, without field work practice it is impossible to understand social work profession properly. There are various reasons behind this poor condition of field work practice:

- Lack of planning,
- Poor quality of supervision,
- Poor model of field work practice,
- Old curriculum followed by the institutions,
- Gap between supervisor and trainee,
- Identification of place for training,
- Lack of interest,
- Lack of commitment,
- Lack of coordination,
- Low motivational level,
- Attitude and perception of trainee [3].

VIII. SPECIALIZATION PROVIDED BY SOCIAL WORK INSTITUTIONS

In most of the institutions various specializations are offered. On the basis of specialization, social work trainees are placed on the field. Some common and specializations of social work education are:

- Human Resource Management/ Personnel Management/ Industrial Relation and Labour Laws/ Industrial Social Work/ Industrial Relation and Personnel Management
- Community Development/ Rural Development
- Medical and Psychiatric Social Work
- Family and Child Welfare
- Social Work in Correctional Field

These are the main specialization provided by social work institutions in India. MSW/BSW/ MA (Social Work). In social work we have different curriculum in all specialization theoretical and practical. Students are placed in agency or community on the basis of their specialization [7].

IX. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To design a model of field work practicum in the field of Labour Welfare.
- To understand the role of social worker to maximize the welfare of workers in industry.

X. NEED OF THIS MODEL AND STUDY

This study plays an important role in enhancing the field work curriculum in the field of Human Resource Management, especially in the field of labour welfare. Labour welfare is not only required in industrial setting, but it is necessary in un-organised sector too, where workers are not getting social security provisions, welfare provisions. Field

work practice in the field of labour welfare is not sound because of lack of field work guidelines and improper supervision. There is an immediate need to design the model of field work curriculum to enhance skills of professional social worker and to aware the workers regarding welfare and safety provisions. In this way this particular study is useful for both social worker and labour perspective.

TABLE I
FIELD WORK PRACTICE OF LABOUR LEGISLATION [8]-[12]

S. No.	Labour Legislation	Field work day	Observation and Verification	Expected Outcome
I.	General		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Organizational visit ➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1) ➤ Definitions (Sec 2) 	Understanding of organization
II.	Factories Act, 1948		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Approval ➤ Licensing and registration (Sec 6) ➤ Occupier (Sec 7) ➤ Health provision (Sec 11-20) ➤ Safety provisions (Sec 21-41) ➤ Welfare provisions (Sec 42-50), ➤ Working hour and leave, ➤ And other important provisions ➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1), ➤ Definitions (Sec 2), ➤ Liability of employer for compensation (Sec 3) ➤ Amount of compensation (Sec 4), ➤ Method of calculating wages (Sec 5) 	<p>Trainees will learn applicability of factories act and process of establishing factory</p> <p>Applicability of health and safety provisions</p> <p>Applicability of welfare provisions and working hours and leave</p> <p>Applicability of Act, scope, employers' responsibility, amount of compensation and calculation of wages</p>
III.	Employees Compensation Act, 1923		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Distribution of compensation (Sec 4A,6,7,8) ➤ Notice of claim (Sec 9), Fatal accident (Sec 10), ➤ Medical examination. (Sec 11) ➤ Special provisions relating to masters and seamen etc. (Sec 15, 15A) ➤ And other important provisions ➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1), ➤ Definitions (Sec 2), ➤ Registration of trade union (Sec 3), ➤ Mode of registration (Sec 4,5) ➤ Rules of TU (Sec 6), ➤ Registration (Sec 8,9), ➤ Cancellation of registration (Sec 10) ➤ Appeal ➤ Registered office. (Sec 12) ➤ Certain acts not to apply to registered trade unions (Sec 14) 	<p>Process of distributing compensation, how to claim, about fatal accident, medical examination and special provisions</p> <p>Applicability of act, process how to register a TU, rules of TU, cancellation provisions of TU,</p>
IV.	Trade Union Act, 1926		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Objects on which general funds may be spent (Sec 15) ➤ Constitution of a separate fund for political purposes (Sec 16) ➤ rights of minors to membership of trade unions (Sec 21) ➤ Proportion of office bearers to be connected with the industry (Sec 22) ➤ Change of name and notice of change (Sec 23, 25) ➤ Amalgamation of trade unions (Sec 24) ➤ Dissolution and Returns (Sec27, 28) ➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1), ➤ Definitions (Sec 2), ➤ Responsibility of wages payment (Sec 3), ➤ Wage period and time of payment (Sec 4,5) 	<p>Which act is not applied to register TU? Where to spend general fund? provision of separate political fund, who can be a member of TU? What shall be the proportion of office bearer, how to change TU? how to merge two or more TU? How to dissolve and submit return of TU?</p> <p>Applicability of Act, who is responsible for wage payment and maximum wage period, permissible deductions under the act.</p>
V.	Payment of Wages Act, 1936		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Deductions permissible from wages (Sec 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 12A), ➤ Maintenance of registers and records (Sec 13A) ➤ Inspectors (Sec 14) ➤ Appeal (Sec 17) ➤ and other important provisions ➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1) ➤ Definitions (Sec 2) 	<p>Who and how to maintain the register, provisions related to the inspector and appeal.</p>
VI.	Industrial Disputes Act, 1947		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Works committee (Sec 3) ➤ Conciliation officer, duties and power (Sec 4,12,13) ➤ Board of conciliation, duties and powers, (Sec 5) 	<p>Applicability of act,</p> <p>Duties, functions and authorities of board,</p>

S. No.	Labour Legislation	Field work day	Observation and Verification	Expected Outcome	
VII.	Minimum Wages Act, 1948		➤ Court of enquiry (Sec 6),	court and tribunal, provisions related to strike and lockout	
			➤ Labour court (Sec 7)		
			➤ Tribunal and national tribunal (Sec 7A, 7B)		
			➤ Duties and powers of all authorities	Provisions related to lay off, retrenchment, closure and penalty	
			➤ Strike and lockout (Sec 23,24,25)		
			➤ Lay off, retrenchment and closure (Sec 25A to 25U)		
			➤ Penalties		
			➤ And other important provisions		
			➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1)		
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2)		
			➤ Fixation and revision of minimum rates of wages (Sec 3)		Applicability of act, how to fix and revise rate of wages,
			➤ Procedure of fixation of minimum wages (Sec 5)		
			➤ Wages in kind (Sec 11)		Provisions related to the committee and sub-committee, functions of advisory board and CAB
			➤ Committees, sub committees		
			➤ Advisory board, central advisory board (Sec 7,8,9)		
➤ And other important provisions					
➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1)					
➤ Definitions (Sec 2)					
VIII.	Employees Provident Fund And Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952		➤ Contribution of payment	Applicability of act, how much shall be the contribution, EPFS, provisions related to central board, executive committee and state board, appointment of officers	
			➤ Employees provident fund scheme		
			➤ Central board (Sec 5A)		
			➤ Executive committee (Sec 5AA)		
			➤ State board (Sec 5B)		
			➤ Board of trustees to be body corporate (Sec 5C)		
			➤ Appointment of officers (Sec 5D)	Provisions of pension scheme and insurance scheme, how and where to present the scheme, constitution, functions and terms of appellate tribunal, how to transfer account?	
			➤ Contributions and matters which may be provided for in the scheme (Sec6)		
			➤ Employees' pension scheme (Sec 6A)		
			➤ Employees' deposit linked insurance scheme (Sec6C)		
			➤ Laying of schemes before parliament (Sec 6D)		
			➤ Employees' provident funds appellate tribunal (Sec7D)		
			➤ Term of office (Sec7E)		
			➤ Transfer of accounts (Sec17A)		
			➤ Employees pension scheme, employees deposit linked scheme,		
➤ And other important provisions	Applicability of act, constitution, functions and terms of ESIC, standing committee, MBC				
➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),					
➤ Definitions (Sec 2),					
➤ ESIC (Sec 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)					
➤ Standing committee (Sec 8, 9)					
➤ Medical benefit council (Sec 10)					
IX.	ESI Act 1948		➤ Sickness benefit	Provisions related to the benefits under the act, contribution under the act	
			➤ Maternity benefit		
			➤ Disablement benefit		
			➤ Dependent benefit		
			➤ Medical benefit and		
			➤ Funeral benefit		
			➤ Contribution of their payment (Sec 39)		
			➤ And other important provisions		
			➤ Scope and applicability		
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2)		
			➤ Act to have overriding effect (Sec 3)		Applicability of act, how it has overriding effect, duty of employer for equal wages and no discrimination during recruitment, constitution and functions of advisory committee, provisions related to the inspector
			➤ Duty of employer to pay equal remuneration (Sec 4)		
			➤ No discrimination to be made while recruiting men and women workers (Sec 5)		
			➤ Advisory committee (Sec 6)		Applicability of act, when the women are prohibited for employment, provisions related to the eligibility for maternity benefit,
			➤ Inspectors (Sec 9)		
➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),					
➤ Definitions (Sec 2),					
➤ Prohibition of employment of women in certain period (Sec 4,6),					
➤ Eligibility of maternity benefit (Sec 5,18),					
XI.	Maternity Benefit Act, 1961		➤ Rate and duration of maternity benefit (Sec 5,7,5a),	Condition for leave with wages, facilities related to maternity benefit	
			➤ Leave and wages in other condition of women (Sec 9,10),		
			➤ Facilities related maternity (Sec 8,11,12,13), and		
XII.	Payment of Bonus Act, 1965		➤ Other important provisions	Applicability of act, how to calculate gross profit, available surplus and bonus?	
			➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),		
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2),		

S. No.	Labour Legislation	Field work day	Observation and Verification	Expected Outcome
XIII.	Industrial Employment (Standing Order) Act, 1946		➤ Computation of gross profits (Sec 4)	Who is eligible and disqualified for bonus, payment of minimum and maximum bonus, provisions of set off and set on
			➤ Computation of available surplus (Sec 5)	
			➤ Sums deductible from gross profits (Sec 6)	
			➤ Calculation of direct tax payable by the employer (Sec 7)	
			➤ Eligibility for bonus (Sec 8)	
			➤ Disqualification for bonus (Sec 9)	
			➤ Payment of minimum bonus (Sec 10)	
			➤ Payment of maximum bonus (Sec 11)	
			➤ Set on and setoff of allocable surplus (Sec15)	
			➤ And other important provisions	
			➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),	
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2)	
			➤ Submission of draft standing orders (Sec 3)	
			➤ Conditions for certification of standing orders (Sec 4)	
XIV.	The Gratuity Act, 1972		➤ Certification of standing orders (Sec 5)	Applicability of act, procedure to submit and prepare draft of standing order, conditions and certification of SO, provisions related to appeal, posting of SO, procedure and duration of modification of SO, provisions related to subsistence allowance
			➤ Appeals (Sec 6)	
			➤ Posting of standing orders (Sec 9)	
			➤ Duration and modification of standing orders (Sec 10)	
			➤ Payment of subsistence allowance (Sec 10A)	
			➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),	
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2)	
			➤ Continuous service (Sec 2A)	
			➤ Controlling authority (Sec 3)	
			➤ Payment of gratuity (Sec 4)	
XV.	Contract Labour Act, 1970	XVII.	➤ Compulsory insurance (Sec 4A)	Applicability of act, what is continuous service? Who is controlling authority, payment of gratuity, provision of compulsory insurance, how to confirm nomination, determination of gratuity amount, provisions related to inspector and recovery of gratuity
			➤ Power to exempt (Sec 5)	
			➤ Nomination (Sec 6)	
			➤ Determination of the amount of gratuity (Sec 7)	
			➤ Inspectors (Sec 7A)	
			➤ Recovery of gratuity (Sec 8)	
			➤ Scope and applicability (Sec 1),	
			➤ Definitions (Sec 2)	
			➤ Central advisory board (Sec 3)	
			➤ State advisory board (Sec 4)	
XVI.	Contract Labour Act, 1970	XVII.	➤ Power to constitute committees (Sec 5)	Applicability of act, constitutions and functions of central and state advisory board, power to constitute committee, how to appoint registering officer and register establishment? How to evocate registration? Prohibition of employment of contract labour
			➤ Appointment of registering officers (Sec 6)	
			➤ Registration of certain, establishments (Sec 7)	
			➤ Revocation of registration in certain cases (Sec 8)	
			➤ Effect of non-registration (Sec 9)	
			➤ Prohibition of employment of contract labour (Sec 10)	
			➤ Appointment of licensing officers (Sec 11)	
			➤ Licensing of contractors (Sec 12)	
			➤ Grant of licenses (Sec 13)	
			➤ Revocation, suspension and amendment of licenses (Sec 14)	
XVII.	Contract Labour Act, 1970		➤ Appeal (Sec 15)	How to appoint licensing officer, licensing of contractor and grant of license? process of revocation, suspension and amendment of licences, provisions related to appeal, welfare and health related provisions under act
			➤ Canteens (Sec 16)	
			➤ Restrooms (Sec 17)	
			➤ Other facilities (Sec 18)	
			➤ First aid facilities (Sec 19)	

Analysis of model: This model of field work practicum designed by the research scholar by using main and important provision of labour legislations. Researcher included the guidelines of fourteen labour laws like, factories act, trade union act, employees' compensation act, payment of wages act, standing order act, industrial disputes act, minimum wages act, employees' insurance act, employees' provident fund act, maternity benefit act, payment of wages act, contract labour act, payment of gratuity act, equal remuneration act. This table of guidelines classified into five columns, first column is serial number, second column shows title of the act, third column deals with the field work day, fourth and most important column deals with the guidelines or objective to be applied at

the field, final column of the table is expected outcome day by day as per the objective or guidelines designed under the act.

XI. ROLE OF SOCIAL WORKER

During field work practice in industrial setting a social worker plays several roles. First, social worker collects base line information of all member of the organization from management. This baseline information includes basic personal information to professional information. Collected information always helps him to understand the dynamics of industry i.e. human behaviour, group activities and organizational functioning [13].

Now roles of a social worker can be classified as followed:

- Social worker as a field work trainee,
- Social worker as HR manager,
- Social worker as a welfare officer,
- Social worker as educator,
- Social worker as an awareness generator,
- Social worker as a counselor,
- Social worker as a researcher,
- Social worker as a negotiator,
- Social worker as mediator.

XII.CONCLUSION

On the basis of above discussion we can say that labour welfare is a specialisation of social work profession. In this particular paper research scholar designed a model of field work practicum in the field of labour welfare to strengthen the field work practice. This is a proposed model which might be useful for the students in future. Different institutions are offering several specializations like community development, HRM, MPSW, Family and child welfare, etc. But, the field work practice is not developed as it should be. Through this paper researcher made efforts to develop field work practice in the field of labour welfare. To prepare a model researcher used guidelines of labour legislations. Role of social worker is always necessary to enhance the overall functioning of the society. In industries a social worker plays different roles to provide benefit to the workers. Last but not least social work education increases over all social welfare and labour welfare is a part of social welfare and a specialised field of social work profession. This study fulfils the future demands of field work practicum in the field of labour welfare.

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